

Influence of Automated Tape Layering (ATL) parameters over permeability and performance for dry CF laminates – CAELESTIS “Hyperconnected simulation ecosystem supporting probabilistic design and predictive manufacturing of next generation aircraft structures”.

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Abstract. One of the main objectives of the CAELESTIS project is to enable the developing and design of new aircraft and engine structures through a digital thread across the manufacturing chain; linking design, production engineering a manufacturing technologies by using simulation and process monitoring technologies. Particularly, CAELESTIS propose the implementation of automated manufacturing technologies as Automated Tape layering (ATL) with dry fiber, and Out of Autoclave (OoA) techniques as Resin Transfer Molding, to produce structural components in cost effective methods.

ATL process has the advantage of producing high-performance components and reducing the manufacturing time and defects introduced in the final material, but its process parameters can influence over the later resin injection process, affecting its performance. Main AFP process parameters are: deposition velocity, head pressure and temperature distribution for binder activation, also during the process, some defects appear over the material: tape gaps, overlaps and fiber misalignment, affecting the local permeability for the dry CF reinforcement, thus possibly introducing more defects. In order to establish a possible correlation between ATL process parameters and RTM performance, some CF coupons were manufactured varying the ATL parameters and introducing some typical defects to study the influence over the permeability of the dry fiber and the later influence in the mechanical performance. Both ATL and RTM process are monitored in-situ, giving relevant information for further use on simulation and design optimization.